

“A STUDY AN IMPACT OF HUNDRED UNITS’ FREE ELECTRICITY SCHEME BY TAMIL NADU STATE GOVERNMENT WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE CITY”

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ABSTRACT

This one of the schemes introduced by former chief minister Jayalalithaa was the hundred units of free electricity. This scheme is still very useful for the lower and also for middle class people. This study is to know about the scheme and units consumed by household people and to know about the benefits and level of satisfaction. To know the benefits initialized under this scheme. The know level of satisfaction this scheme in this study no of responds is 120. The came to know that people are more convenient in paying bills through online. Therefore, the value of electricity is much more important in India.

INTRODUCTION

The scheme of hundred units of free electricity, announced by former Chief Minister Jayalalithaa as part of her election campaign during the Assembly election in 2016, the loss suffered by the Tamil Nadu Generation and Distribution Corporation (Tangedco) for the financial year 2017-18, to the extent of 7,760 crore, is being attributed to the reduction in average cost of realisation, both in the high-tension and low-tension categories. The loss of 7,760 crore in 2017-18 compares with 4,348 crore in 2016-17. Experts had hoped that in the wake of debt being taken over by the State government under the ‘UDAY’ scheme, the losses would be minimised. However, they have only increased. Though Tangedco has been able to increase its total revenue by 2,578 crores

in 2017-18, from a total revenue of 56,012 crore in 2016-17, the revenue from the sale of power in 2017-18 has gone down by 277.63 crore to 43,686 crore

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the factors influencing the scheme
- To know the units consumed by household people
- To know the benefits under this scheme.
- To know the level of satisfaction this scheme

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- Coimbatore City alone is selected to conduct this survey to lack of time and cost involved in collected the information from various areas.
- The research was carried out in a short period of time.
- Limited simple size 120 respondents.

SCOPE OF STUDY:

- This study can help the beneficiary to get awareness to the scheme
- This study can give knowledge about how effective to get satisfaction for the scheme

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to achieve the objective, the data are collected from the consumers. The methodology of research is clearly explained below the primary data collected in the survey are subject to proper analytical study.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The data was collected for Coimbatore city

PRIMARY DATA

Primary data are collected by conducting direct structured interview by using questionnaires, it means all respondents are asked the same questions in the same fashion and they are informed the purpose of the study.

SECONDARY DATA

Secondary data is collected from journals, magazines and books, newspaper and internet.

AREA OF STUDY: This study was conducted in Coimbatore city.

SAMPLING METHOD: Convenient sampling method is used.

SAMPLE SIZE: The sample size is 120.

TOOLS USED FOR ANALYSIS: Data analysing tools are Simple percentage and Chi-square test.

DESCRIPTION OF RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design adopted in the study was descriptive design, which is concerned with the descriptive of a group. In descriptive research in such a way that the respondents is able to understand clearly what the researcher wants and provides descriptive to measure the data.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

DEHRADUN (2021) A head of next year's assembly elections, the Uttarahand government has announced 100 units of free electricity for domestic consumers. The announcement was made by newly-appointed power minister Harak Singh Rawat after he chaired a meeting of officials of the electricity department on Wednesday.

P Thangamani (2021) on Saturday clarified the various observations made in the report of the Comptroller and Auditor General of India on public sector undertakings for the year ending March 31, 2019, tabled in the State Assembly on June 24. Thangamani said nowhere in the report it is said that corruption took place during this period. The media has been exaggerating these observation

Raju & Rao (2017) studied the impact of power sector reforms in AP and concluded that power sector reforms have positive impact on

Transmission and distribution. They also hold the view that the state sector generation had decreased during reform period

D. Sa et. al. (2016) found that the Indian power sector was opened to private participation in 1991 to hasten the increase in generating capacity and to improve the system efficiency as well. However they revealed that some important problems have not been addressed such as an addition to the generation capacity without corresponding improvement of the transmission

and distribution facilities is likely to further undermine system efficiency. They also stated that investment in infrastructure has been a responsibility of state governments because intrinsically long gestation periods coupled with the relatively low rates of return from serving all categories of consumers had rendered such projects commercially unviable.

Demographic profile of the respondents

S.no	Demographic		No of respondents	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	66	55
		Female	54	45
2	Age group	Below 30 years	6	5
		30-40 years	84	70
		40-50 years	17	14
		Above 50 years	13	11
3	Qualification	School level	6	5
		Graduate	66	55
		Post Graduate	30	25
		other	18	15
4	occupation details	agriculture	20	17
		business	56	46
		professional	19	16
		salaries	25	21
5	Marital status	Married	93	78
		Un married	27	23

Interpretation: Table 1 clearly states the demographic profile of the sample respondents. Majority of the responds fall in the age group of 30-40 and most of them are male. Majority of them graduate. Majority of the respondent's occupation has business. Most of the respondents are married.

Chi- Square Analysis Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2/E_i$$

Degree of freedom = (r-1) (c-1)

H₁-There is significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and their convenient of bill paying of the respondent

Chi-Square Table

O	E	(O-E) ²	(O _i - E _i) ² /E _i
28	26.95	1.103	0.041
21	22.05	1.103	0.050
0	0	0	0
24	23.65	0.123	0.005
19	19.35	0.123	0.006
0	0	0	0
14	15.4	1.96	0.127
14	12.6	1.96	0.156
0	0	0	0

	total	0.385
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Source: primary data

Significant level = 0.05

Result: calculate the chi-square value is (0.385) is less than (9.488) table value hence the hypothesis is accepted Therefore, it is found that there is significant relationship between respondents' gender and their convenient of bill paying of the respondents.

H₁: There is significant relationship between qualification of the respondents and the number of NPTEL courses enrolled.

Chi-Square Table

O	E	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	(O _i - E _i) ² /E _i
14	12.98	1.02	1.040	0.080
10	9.81	0.19	0.036	3.669
11	11.08	0.08	6.4	0.577
3	4.116	1.116	1.245	0.302
8	8088	0.88	0.774	0.087

7	6.71	0.29	0.084	0.0125
9	7.58	1.42	2.016	0.205
2	2.816	0.816	0.665	0.235
10	11.27	1.27	1.612	0.143
8	8.525	0.525	0.275	0.032
12	9.62	2.38	5.664	0.588
3	3.57	0.57	0.324	0.090
9	7.85	1.15	1.322	0.168

6	5.94	0.06	3..6	0.600
3	6.708	3.704	13.71	2.048
5	2.491	2.491	6.295	2.529
		Total		11.425

Source: primary data

Result: The calculate chi-square value is (11.425) is less than (16.919) table value hence the hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is significant relationship between income level of the respondents and the scheme amount of electricity consumed by the respondents.

Results and Discussion Simple Percentage Analysis

1. Majority 55% of the respondents are male.
2. Majority 70% of the respondent's age between 30-40 years.
3. Majority 55% of the respondents are Qualification is Graduate.
4. 46% of the respondents are occupation is business.
5. Majority 78% of the respondents are married.
6. Majority 80 % of the respondents are nuclear family.
7. Majority 69% of the respondents has 2 members in their family.
8. Majority 66% of the respondents are qualification in others.
9. 34% of the respondent's monthly income between 10000,20000.

10. Majority 68% of the respondents are salaried people
11. Majority 88% of the respondents earning 1-2 member in family
12. Majority 96% of the respondents are known about this scheme
13. Majority 82% of the respondents using more electricity for washing machine and refrigerator.
14. 96% of the respondents using Domestic purpose.
15. Majority 55% of the respondents known slab rate of this scheme.
16. Majority 74% of the respondents has paid rs200-500.
17. 40% of the respondents convenient to pay in direct payment.
18. Majority 89% of the respondents cc deposit is refundable.
19. Majority 57% of the respondents has Digital type of junction box is used.
20. Majority 95% of the respondents you not use sub-meter.

Chi-Square

The Calculated the chi square value at (5%) level of significant is (0.385) is lesser than table value (9.488) hence the hypothesis is accepted .Therefore there is significant

relationship between gender of the respondents and their convenient to pay bill.

The calculated chi square value at (5%) level of significant is (11.425) is lesser than the table value (16.919) hence the hypothesis is accepted .Therefore there is significant relationship between income of the respondents and their scheme amount of electricity consumed by the respondents.

SUGGESTIONS

- As the electricity consumption is high so the 100 units which have been given by the government can be increased
- If electricity board is handover to the private institution the free units that is given can be continued
- The rate of the electricity can be reduced

CONCLUSION

The study conducted in Coimbatore city electricity board. I can say that lower and lower middle people is fulfilling the needs so this scheme is useful for the people. And event the free units that is given can be increased .most of the domestic users are beneficiary and even Commercial users are suffering without this free units. And people are convenient in paying bills through online. Therefore, value of electricity is important in India

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